

**METHODS THAT ARE UP-TO-DATE FOR TEACHING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES IN PRESCHOOL.**

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Abstract:

This article highlights the great importance attached to modern vocational education. This does not exclude the process of preschool education. Method of sign and image, method of sound recognition and adaptation, method of organization with natural world, a method of adaptation of inactive students. methods of teaching foreign languages in the process of preschool education in the Republic the method of signs and images, the method of recognition and comparison of voice, the method of learning with Uzbekistan, as well as modern teaching methods necessary for their organization. "Either we are preparing for life or for exams. We will choose the first one. he stressed. He recently talked about the local education system and principles, and shared his thoughts on why Finnish education is considered one of the best in the world. At present, giving

Key words: Foreign language in preschool education, Finnish education system, 387 Scientific April 2021 / Volume 2 Issue 4 journal "Science and Education" www.openscience.uz Machine Translated by Google I also want to point out that in order to help you succeed, we ask early childhood education professionals to share their favorite strategies for teaching children. a few small but not too big things that start with these letters. For example, if your letters are M and K, and you have a cat and an elephant. Start by telling your child about the sound a cat makes. Then invite the child to find something that starts with the same sound and glue it to the letter. ways to build everyday vocabulary is to have children verbally name common brands and symbols. He explains that translating pictures into words helps Children are very interested in learning lessons in a natural environment. As a rule, the garden in the back environment. Think twice before asking students to draw their families: language development. That is, it helps children a lot to learn new languages quickly and easily. 2. Voice recognition and matching method. backyard can be a great way to educate them about the natural world. This growing method In addition, he creates a "masterpiece". think about how an adopted or estranged child might feel and how others learned by heart in kindergarten. However, this causes problems for some children. 3. A way to get used to the natural world. According to Dr. Elaine Vogel Schneider, director of Touchtime International, one of Gretzinger says

children should be empathetic to children in non-traditional home younger age. This list of learning strategies for the preschool classroom provides excellent transitional opportunities to grow and learn as a teacher. Decorated letters can be left in the classroom or taken home to share with parents. Schneider said it is a favorite activity for students because it gives them hands-on learning. You can easily return to the teacher's textbook or regular lessons that you plants from seed to maturity is important not only for children to learn about their growth, but For this activity, you will need some large letters cut out of cardboard and means spiritual development [interesting information about the Finnish education system]. I and so that they quickly and easily learn words in a foreign language. This method removes children can respond to need. Inclusive activities can take a little longer to complete, especially at the beginning of the year when you are all stress and also helps improve fine motor skills. Machine Translated by Google 1. Methods of working with characters and pictures. Scientific April 2021 / Volume 2 Issue 4 journal "Science and Education" www.openscience.uz 388 4. The method of adapting one's activities to students. Machine Translated by Google You may not know your students, but you can tell when you screw up that your child is embarrassed. In this, the educator must continue his creativity. Preschool education is the first step in the education and upbringing of our youth. The right preschool program should help our children grow and learn in a way that suits their unique intelligence. But children, unlike adults, do not plan the future, tomorrow. The English lesson should be conducted in the sense of "here and now." Children learn a foreign language more easily by making sense of stories or winning games. If they want, they can enhance their organ information through games with their participation. On the one hand, the content expressed in the language should be related to the life and daily life of children, on the other hand, activities or tasks that invite children to communicate should be interesting and important. During the lesson, students become aware of being part of the lesson and behave and act like the characters in the play during the lesson. In primary school, foreign language teaching is usually very effective and successful when it is organized using action methods based on life situations and games. If learning a foreign language is carried out through plot-game situations, then all children will participate willingly, as they feel part of the situation. Pupils "live" with a foreign language, first of all, in small classes. Therefore, if it is possible to communicate in the classroom, then it should be in a foreign language. Children can not only understand instructions, but also express their needs through a foreign language. In this regard, it is

useful to communicate with English-speaking people (native speakers of English) and invite them to the class. According to the constructive approach, children should learn the meaning of words and rules in as many languages as possible. It also helps them develop basic thinking skills. Like all learners, children have different learning styles. Talim for kids takes into account all styles of talim. Tactical and kinesthetic types of training require special attention from the student. In elementary schools, students have a wider range of talents, skills, knowledge and interests. Learning a foreign language also depends on the student's ability to understand well. While learning a foreign language, it is necessary to encourage each child to move. They must develop acoustic, kinesthetic, rhythmic and visual differentiation. Children quickly organize, but therefore, by repeating a speech several times, you can help children remember it through games or handouts. Courses are spiral, and regular repetitions are an integral part. Successful foreign language teaching requires complex methods. amount of communication and Machine Translated by Google 389 Scientific April 2021 / Volume 2 Issue 4 journal "Science and Education" www.openscience.uz Machine Translated by Google Machine Translated by Google characteristic of a foreign language, texts and texts capable of conveying culture languages?]. - 2019. - 260 p.] [Mustafoeva, S.S. Learning and teaching foreign languages: how children master learn new ways. Learning foreign languages opens up new Many children are interested in learning foreign languages. Their interest, of course, is connected with the organization of the educational process and the ability of children to achieve certain success in this educational process. It is wrong to assume that this interest will remain unchanged for many years, so teachers need to take care of it, that is, make sure that the participants are happy and successful in the lesson. The content and purpose of the lesson will be clear and memorable to the participants only if the organized topics, as well as the questions, are important, interesting and relevant for the participants. Foreign language teachers are faced with a different language and culture in teaching a foreign language. For this reason, it is recommended to use reliable materials, opportunities in the future, they become qualified personnel, Successful teaching of foreign languages also depends on how skillfully children worthy of their homeland and strong personalities in the future. We need to give more attention to the education of our children, to create modern conditions, to help them the teacher uses the opportunities available to him. Students should be given assignments such that they are forced to apply and retain their organic knowledge during the lesson.

Communication skills are important for developing language skills. Social interaction, especially when students are able to apply the meaning of language, allows them to use language effectively. The teacher's ability to communicate and negotiate for this process is one of the main conditions for successful learning. Foreign language education, first of all, should encourage the organization of everyday, real knowledge and knowledge of a foreign language, but the development of specific knowledge cannot be neglected. If we dwell on the methodological and didactic views used in teaching a foreign language, then it is necessary to emphasize the following: the future. quality is the main reason for faster language learning.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, it must be said that the role of preschool education students' attention should be mainly focused on the content and significance of the language. Students should focus primarily on the content of the language. important in the development of our children. We must provide them with modern technologies and a modern education system. Preschool education is of great importance for the development of the roots of each person in society, that is, for him to grow up.

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